

Paradigms of the "Arithmometer" for Direct Multiplication by Georgy Nikoladze

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Article History:

Received: 24.04.2025 Revised: 28.05.2025 Accepted: 31.05.2025 Published: 02.06.2025

ABSTRACT:

The article presents the operating principles of the "Direct Multiplication and Division Electrical Arithmometer" patented by Georgy Nikoladze in Paris in 1928. It discusses the essence of direct decimal multiplication, the method developed by G. Nikoladze for implementing the principles of direct multiplication in an electrical device, and the algorithm he devised for performing division based on the multiplication operation. A concept for reconstructing G. Nikoladze's arithmometer is presented, along with an analysis of several authentic nodes of the reconstructed device. The conclusion is made that: G. Nikoladze's patent application accurately reflects the truth of the ideas embedded in it; G. Nikoladze's invention was a serious breakthrough in computer technologies for the beginning of the 20th century; the idea of direct multiplication remains relevant today.

Keywords: Georgy Nikoladze, arithmometer, direct multiplication, Genaille's multiplication rulers.

Suggested Citation: L. Imnaishvili, M. Bedineishvili, G. Goderdzishvili, G. Zedginidze, "Paradigms of the "Arithmometer" for Direct Multiplication by Georgy Nikoladze," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(3), pp. 254-267, May-Jun 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(3).17

INTRODUCTION

Today, the prevailing opinion is that Georgy Nikoladze deserves considerable credit for his contributions [1,2]:

- in metallurgy;
- in mathematics (linear geometry);
- in sports (mountaineering, gymnastics).

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Nikoladze was not given an opportunity to continue his work. He passed away at an early age in 1931.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Essence of Georgy Nikoladze's Invention

First, let's find out what Nikoladze patented and later implemented. The device patented by Nikoladze is not exactly an arithmometer in the modern sense; it is a direct multiplication and division device, although the patent indicates that the device must work in conjunction with an addition/subtraction device.

Until the 1920s, there was no direct multiplication device; multiplication was performed through sequential addition (this is still the case in digital computers today). Thus, the problem of accelerating multiplication existed. Patent [3] describes the principles of multiplying a single-digit multiplier by a multi-digit multiplicand. The author believes that the addition of the resulting partial products is not a problem. We do not know whether the device implemented in the form of a prototype was solely a multiplication device or if it was intended to work in tandem with an adder/subtractor, as no description or diagram of the prototype have been preserved.

Therefore, Nikoladze patented a device for direct multiplication of a single-digit multiplier by a multi-digits multiplicand. The operation is not mechanical but rather electromechanical. Here we should be specific: the installation of the multi-digits and single-digit multipliers is mechanical and carried out by the user, while the actual multiplication occurs by passing electronic signals through the circuits.

The Essence of Georgy Nikoladze's Arithmetic Operation

Nikoladze's computing device is based on the principle of the French engineer Genaille's calculating rulers for multiplication (see Figure 2) [5]. The principle of Genaille's multiplication is a kind of "multiplication table", which, with a specific arrangement of the rulers for the multiplicands and the selection of a multiplier (a single digit), allows to quickly find the product of multiplication. The multiplier rulers are arranged according to the decimal positional system, i.e. from right to left.

Figure 2. Obtaining the Partial Product with the Genaille Rulers

To understand the answer to the product, we must take the horizontal line that corresponds to the multiplier digit. The multiplied answer is read from right to left. Figure 2 shows the arrangement of the multiplier rulers for the number 567,439. Accordingly, the ruler corresponding to the digit 9 is placed on the right, and the ruler of the higher-order digit 5 is placed on the left. To understand the multiplication answer, we should take the horizontal bar that represents the digit of the multiplier. In this case, the digit of the multiplier taken is 3. Unlike the usual rule of multiplication, in this case the answer of the product is "read" from right to left. The first digit of the product in the smallest sequence

is always the uppermost digit of the field (it does not matter which of the fields 1-9 we are considering). In this case, the digit is 7. The next digit of the sequence is indicated by the vertex of the triangle in the field of this sequence. So the next digit of the multiplication is 1. The next digit of the multiplier indicates the third triangle of the next field, where the least significant digit of the result should be selected. So, the next multiplier of the multiplication will be 3. The result of reading all the digits of the multiplication will be the answer - 1,702,317. If the digit of the multiplier had been 5, the multiplication answer would have been 2,837,195 (Figure 2).

If the multiplier is multi-digit, the Genaille rulers must be used to find the partial products for each digit of the multiplier, and then these partial products must be summed in a shifted manner. We note that the Genaille rulers cannot perform the shifting and summation of the partial products.

In Patent [3], Georgy Nikoladze describes the device that can only obtain partial products. He specifies the necessity of multiplication and addition processes for obtaining the product. Thus, Georgy Nikoladze's arithmetic multiplication operation is performed for us in a traditional way which is familiar to us.

As for the division operation, whose feasibility is indicated by the title of the patent, the author of the patent considers that the division operation should be performed through the multiplication operation. The specific way of performing this operation is also shown.

Algorithm of the Method of Division Proposed by Georgy Nikoladze

- Divisor (conditionally a multiplicand) is multiplied by 9 or its decimal multiple so that the product is closer to the divisor (the difference between them should not be greater or equal to the divisor), but not greater than the divisor;
- The multiplicand, which is the first partial quotient, is stored;
- The product will be subtracted from the dividend, and the first partial remainder will be obtained;
- The divisor (conditionally the product) is again multiplied by 9 (conditionally the multiplicand) or by its decuple. If as a result of multiplying by 9 the product turned out to be greater than the partial remainder, one less than 9 is taken instead, i.e., 8. If the same case is repeated with 8, then an even smaller digit is taken;
- Partial quotient will be stored again;
- The obtained multiplication product is subtracted from the initial partial remainder;
- Obtain the second remainder and so on until the remainder is less than the divisor;
- The quotient is obtained by summing the stored partial quotients.

Due to the unusualness of the method of division, we considered it necessary to give an example.

Dividend: 7759

Divisor: 59

- First step: $59 * 90 = 5310$, the first remainder: $7759 - 5310 = 2449$, the first quotient - 90.
- Second step: $59 * 9 = 531$, second remainder: $2449 - 531 = 1918$, second quotient - 9;
- Third step: $59 * 9 = 531$, third remainder: $1918 - 531 = 1387$, third quotient - 9;
- Fourth step: $59 * 9 = 531$, fourth remainder: $1387 - 531 = 856$, fourth quotient - 9;
- Fifth step: $59 * 9 = 531$, fifth remainder: $856 - 531 = 325$, fifth quotient - 9;
- Sixth step: $59 * 5 = 295$; sixth remainder $325 - 295 = 30$, sixth quotient - 5;
- Seventh step: sum of quotients $90 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 5 = 131$.

Quotient is 131.

Remainder is 30.

Georgy Nikoladze's "Direct Multiplication and Division Electronic Arithmometer" Reconstruction Concept [6]

As we found out above, Georgy Nikoladze's patent "Direct Multiplication and Division Electronic Arithmometer" describes only the method and device for automating partial multiplication and private divisions. The same patent states that this device must work in tandem with an addition/subtraction device, about which we don't know how it was constructed.

Thus, we considered that based on the patent only the "Direct Multiplication and Division Electronic Arithmometer" can be restored in a close to authentic form. We also consider that presenting it in this form would not be interesting or engaging for a 21st-century viewer.

Therefore, the following approach is suggested:

- "Direct multiplication and division electronic arithmometer" were restored in authentic form;
- A personal computer works in tandem with it, tasked with performing the function of summing/subtracting the partial products/quotients and obtaining the product/quotient.

According to the patent, the reproduction mechanism of Genaille's rulers was transferred to discs of a special design. By turning the discs, the multiplicand is also "dialed". Following the mechanism of Genaille's multiplication, a mechanism was developed that allows current to be delivered to a certain location on the disc and output to a certain location as well. The location of the power supply on the disk corresponds to the digit of the partial product.

Almost 100 years have passed since the patent was issued. It is understandable that there have been changes in the approach to the issue, materials, etc.

In order to ensure authenticity, it was proposed to keep special disks, a method of dialing multiplicands with disks.

It is clear that copper material would have been used as current-conducting contacts in Nikoladze's machine, but we do not know what material was used to make the disks. Therefore, we used contemporary technologies and materials to prepare the discs.

Nikoladze imagined the placement of disks and current-carrying circuits in an independent rectangular case so that the disks could be rotated from outside the case (see Figure 3). The case also has power supply terminals (we know a DC power supply was used, but we don't know where it was located) and a contact system for outputting the digits of the partial product.

Figure 3. The External Appearance of Nikoladze's Arithmometer

The architecture of the system - reconstructed arithmometer and personal computer can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. System Architecture of the Reconstructed Arithmometer

Reconstructed Arithmometer Engineering

Based on the architecture of the system and the current technologies, the engineering and realization of the “direct multiplication/division device” were the most difficult from an engineering point of view. Among these difficulties, we would especially highlight the engineering solution of the circuits shown in Figure 4, the methods of displaying the received partial product on the indicators and sending it to the computer, the precision of the disks. These difficulties are indicated even by the constructions and number of contact systems (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Contact System of the Disk

The appearance of the reconstructed arithmometer can be seen in Figure 6.

The user “dials” the set, so in order to increase the ergonomics of spinning the discs, 15 mm wide rims are attached to them from the outside. Since during the “dialing” of the set, the discs require precise alignment to each other, a special lock is used for their correct orientation. In order to rotate the discs, it is necessary to loosen them from each other first, and tighten them after the rotation. For this purpose, the release/clamping lever of the disks is used. A “banana plug” is used to set the multiplier digit (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The External Appearance of the Reconstructed Arithmometer

System in working condition can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The System in Operation

Algorithm for Performing the Multiplication Operation

With the implemented system, it is possible to multiply a three-digit multiplicand by a four-digit multiplier. The number of digit multiplicand is determined by the number of discs in the arithmometer, and the number of digit multiplier is determined by the capabilities of the software product.

To perform a multiplication, the following procedures must be carried out:

- To start multiplication, we use the “Start multiplication” button on the touch screen of the computer;

The multiplicand is typed on the touch monitor with the “Enter multiplicand” button, the virtual keyboard is activated and the user enters the multiplicand (maximum number of digits - 3), which is

reflected in the form of rows in the boxes corresponding to the multiplication process. Entering the number is finished with the Enter button (Figure 8);

Figure 8. Entering Multiplicand

- The multiplier is typed on the touch monitor: the button “Input multiplier” activates the virtual keyboard and the user enters multiplier (maximum number of digits - 4), which is reflected in the form of rows in the boxes corresponding to the multiplication process. Entering the multiplier is finished with the Enter button (Figure 9). Accordingly, the lower exponent of the multiplier takes on a red color. At the same time, the button “Get partial product” will be activated, which indicates that it is now possible to multiply the product by the sequence of units of the multiplier.

Figure 9. Entering Multiplier

- Discs are released with a lever in the device;
- Discs are released for turning with the lock;
- The number is “typed” on the disks (Figure 10): right disk - junior digit, middle disk - next digit, left disk - senior digit (in case of three-digit multiplicand). The digits of multiplicand indicated on the touch monitor is set with disks;

Figure 10. Setting the Multiplier on the Arithmometer

- Discs are fixed with a lock;
- Discs are held with a lever;
- “Banana plug” will include the first digit of the multiplier.
- LEDs corresponding to the partial product will light up on the display of the device;
- Automatically, the information will be exchanged between the device and the computer;
- The touch monitor is affected by the “Get partial product” button. The received partial product I is reflected in the boxes of the first partial product;
- If there are no more digits of the multiplier, the multiplication process ends, otherwise the second number of the multiplier turns red and the “Get partial product” button is activated again;
- It is not necessary to “dial” the multiplier on the device, but it may be necessary to move the “banana plug” in the socket (when the current digit of the multiplier is different from the previous digit). The second partial product will be displayed on the device's display;
- Information will be exchanged between the direct multiplication device and the computer;
- After pressing the button “Receive partial product”, partial product II is received from the direct multiplication device. The second partial product is shifted to the left by one order, which is reflected in the boxes of the second partial product;
- If the multiplier is a three-digit, this cycle will be performed once more. The same applies to the case of a four-digit multiplier;
- After there’s no more digits in the multiplier, the system formats the value of the product with the help of partial products, which it displays in the corresponding cells of the product. For this, you need to use the button "Calculation of the product".
- To start further multiplication, all the above procedures must be performed again.

When receiving a partial product, the multiplier digit is also received from the device to the computer. Based on this data, the multiplicand is calculated and compared with the multiplicand entered in the computer by the user. If the multiplicand and multiplier digit received from the device are different from those entered in the computer, the system will offer the user to correct the multiplicand and multiplier digit entered by him. The user decides whether to change the multiplicand or the multiplier digit. If at the user's decision the multiplicand or any digit of the multiplier changes, the user can continue the multiplication. Otherwise, the user terminates the process and starts over.

Algorithm for Performing the Division Operation

With the system, it is possible to divide a seven-digit dividend by a three-digit divisor.

It is necessary to carry out the following procedures:

- To start the division, we use the “Start division” button;
- On the touch monitor, the dividend is dialed with the “Enter dividend” button (Figure 11). The virtual keyboard is activated and the user enters the dividend (maximum number of digits - 7), which is reflected in the form of rows in the boxes corresponding to the division process;

Figure 11. Inserting the Divisor

- Entering the dividend is finished with the Enter ↵ button;
- The divisor is dialed on the touch monitor: the “Enter divisor” button activates the virtual keyboard and the user enters the digits of the divisor (maximum number of digits - 3), which is reflected in the form of rows in the boxes corresponding to the division process;
- Entering the divisor is finished with the Enter ↵ button;
- The “Find the first quotient” button will be activated (Figure 12). As can be seen from the algorithm, finding a partial quotient is related to finding the product of the divisor and 9 or its decuple;

Figure 12. Activating the First Partial Division Button

- On the arithmometer, the number of the divisor is typed in the form of a multiplicand, and 9 is fixed as the digit of the multiplier (Figure 13). In order to dial the multiplicand, the discs must first

be freed from the lever and the fixator. Next, rotate the discs, then fix them with a lock, and then lock them with a lever. After that, insert the “banana plug” into socket 9;

Figure 13. Finding the First Partial Partition

- In the sub-window, we need to activate the "Find the first partial quotient" button. As a result, the result of finding the first partial quotient is reflected in a specially allocated field, where the option marked in red is an attempt made by the computer that ended in failure. The first partial quotient, which is a successful option, is given in black color (Figure 14);

Figure 14. Finding the Next Partial Quotients

- Then we use the button “Formation of partial quotients and remainders”. As a result, the next partial quotient already found is automatically recorded in a specially allocated field;
- A sub-window will appear again, where we need to use the “Get product” button. As a result, further partial quotients are automatically formed, but if the multiplier digit - 9 is not acceptable, the computer will suggest changing it to 8, etc. The process continues until the partial quotient is acceptable.
- When the partial quotients are found, the partial divisions sub-window will no longer appear and the “Calculate quotient and remainder” button will be activated. Using it, quotient and remainder are reflected in the corresponding fields (Figure 15).

It should be noted that the automation of finding partial quotients is implemented only to simplify the process. In an authentic device, this was likely done “manually” by the user.

Figure 15. Finding the Quotient and Remainder

RESULTS

Georgy Nikoladze managed to find a simple and universal method of “arranging” of Genaille’s rulers.

As shown above, the Genaille’s ruler corresponding to one digit covers 10 fields vertically. For obvious reasons there are 9 fields in the rulers shown in Figure 2. Besides, in order to obtain a partial product with Genaille’s rulers, it is necessary to arrange the digits of the multiplicand along each other in the appropriate order of the rulers. To generalize, for each digit in the multiplicand, ten digits fields 0-9 are needed in the respective rows of the ruler, since it is not known in advance what digit will be in the sequence of multiplicand.

To implement this process, Georgy Nikoladze divided the circle into ten segments and in each segment “transferred” one Genaille’s ruler from 1 to 9 (Figure 16) [3].

Figure 16. Transferring Genaille's Ten Rulers to Ten Segments of a Circle

One disk represents one digit of the multiplicand divided into ten segments. When arranging as many disks as needed in order, each corresponding to one side, we'll have the same number of sets. The multiplier is always a single digit. Now it is enough to arrange the disks so that the segments corresponding to the digits of the multiplicand appear in parallel, that is, to “assemble” the multiplicand.

Nikoladze was able to find a method of “transferring” the fields of Genaille’s rulers to the segments of the circle.

Each segment of the circle covers all ten fields of the ruler. In each Genaille’s ruler, one field, i.e. one order of the multiplier corresponds to a certain configuration of black triangle(s) (see Figure 16). When sorting a multiplicand with Genaille’s rulers, the rule applies for a specific digit of the multiplier in each ruler: the tip of the triangle of the ruler of the previous order shows the next order of the partial product. An exception is the smallest integer, when the smallest integer of the special product is the uppermost digit of the base of the triangle.

Since individual disks correspond to individual alignments of the set, these configurations must be located next to each other on the disks during “typing” of the set. In today’s terminology, the current entry and exit points are defined in the disk segments, that is, after arranging the circles, the current conduction track is obtained (see Figure 17). The multiplier is typed by pressing one of the ten keys. A current will flow through the circuit and a voltage will be obtained at certain contacts to be supplied to the adder/subtractor and indicator lamps.

Figure 17. Transferring the Fields of Genaille's Rulers to Each Segment

Thus, Nikoladze decided to tackle several difficult challenges for that period:

- For the first time it was possible to create an electrical device for direct multiplication;
- For the first time, he was able to get out of the “captivity” of the principles used in mechanical arithmetic meters and chose another way for obtaining the product;
- For the first time, it was possible to get the answer of an arithmetic operation instantly;
- Decided on the original constructions of connecting electrical circuits and carrying current.

DISCUSSION

We did not conduct a comparative analysis of the fast operation of the reconstructed direct multiplication “arithmometer” with the traditional method of sequential partial product assembly, as we considered that the direct multiplication method is much faster.

The evolution of computer technology took place based on the analogies of arithmetic operations common in arithmometers existing at the beginning of the 20th century. Therefore, it is concluded that even today, the multiplication (and division) operation is performed through the sequential assembly of partial products. This can be explained, on one hand, by the tradition of the method used to perform the multiplication operation, and on the other hand, by the technical simplicity of implementing such a method.

The functionality of the “arithmometer” we reconstructed demonstrates the reality of Georgy Nikoladze's methods of multiplication and division. During the reconstruction, our main objective was

to preserve the authenticity of the principles underlying the operation of G. Nikoladze's "arithmometer", and we did not focus on the efficiency of the device's operation.

As a result, an interesting challenge arises in synthesizing direct multiplication and division with modern technologies and maximum efficiency.

We cannot fail to acknowledge Georgy Nikoladze's genius, which is manifested in the following:

- Perception of multiplication as the problem of successive addition of individual products. This method of multiplication was used in arithmometers of that time and is still performed in computers today. Moreover, it is necessary to add the product as many times (one less) as the number of the multiplicand. At that time, a system of cogs was used to mechanize multiplication, which was unreliable and expensive. In the construction developed by Nikoladze, cogs were not used at all.
- Transfer of Genaille's principle of multiplication to electromechanics, which was regarded as clever, was unconventional for that time;
- It was a significant advance for that time.

CONCLUSION

Research of the reconstructed model proved the reality of the approach, device operation principles, algorithms and constructions presented in Nikoladze's patent application.

The merit of Georgy Nikoladze in the development of computer technologies should not be disputed. It needs to be presented properly.

We consider the modern development of Nikoladze's method of direct multiplication and division to be a promising area for further research.

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